

From the Publisher's Desk

Dear Esteemed Readers and Contributors,

It is with great pleasure that I welcome you to the inaugural issue of *Creativitas: Critical Explorations in Literary Studies*. As the Publisher and Founder of *Sapientia*, I am thrilled to see this ambitious project come to fruition.

Sapientia, established in September 2023, has grown into a vibrant community of over 1200 English studies scholars. The launch of *Creativitas* represents the natural evolution of our academic aspirations. As an open-access, multidisciplinary platform, *Creativitas* aims to foster scholarly discourse, advance knowledge, and encourage intellectual diversity in English studies and allied fields.

This journal emerged from within our community, reflecting the collaborative spirit that defines *Sapientia*. We hope *Creativitas* will serve as a cornerstone for our members, providing opportunities for publishing research and engaging in peer review.

I extend my heartfelt gratitude to all who have made this possible. Our dedicated reviewers and editorial board deserve special recognition for their commitment to maintaining high academic standards. I also want to express my sincere thanks to the members of our esteemed Advisory Board for their invaluable insights and guidance.

Special thanks to Dr. Achyut Chetan (Dean of Arts and Social Sciences, St. Xavier's University, Kolkata), Dr. Prayag Ray (Assistant Professor, Department of English, St. Xavier's University), Dr. Bidisha Kantha (Assistant Professor of English, Xavier Law School, St. Xavier's University, Kolkata), and Prof. (Dr.) Ranjan Ghosh (Professor of English, University of North Bengal) for their exceptional support.

To our authors, thank you for your contributions. To the *Sapientia* community, your support has been crucial. I also acknowledge our technical team and administrative staff for their tireless efforts behind the scenes.

As we embark on this journey, I invite all members to engage actively with *Creativitas*. This inaugural issue marks the beginning of a new chapter in our mission to promote collaboration and knowledge advancement in English studies.

Welcome to *Creativitas*!

Arpan Mitra

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